

Human-Centric AI-Enabled Extended Reality
Applications for the Industry 5.0 Era

CLOSING THE LOOP: BIOMETRIC ADAPTATION AND GENERATIVE AI FOR ADAPTIVE XR TRAINING IN
INDUSTRIAL MAINTENANCE

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ABSTRACT

This whitepaper presents the XR5.0 Pilot 5 application for biometric-adaptive XR training in industrial edge device assembly and repair. The pilot integrates Extended Reality, Artificial Intelligence, and Human Digital Twin technologies to deliver a training system that adapts to both the trainee's skill level and their real-time cognitive and physiological state. Two AI functions operate within a closed feedback loop: a Human Digital Twin that models trainee engagement and cognitive load from wearable sensor data, and a constrained generative AI engine that produces structured procedural content grounded in device-specific technical documentation. The system supports both immersive headset-based classroom training and handheld device deployments for field maintenance through a device-agnostic streaming architecture. Two use cases are addressed: personalised training for device assembly and remote-guided repair. A preliminary evaluation with industrial technicians at SPACE Hellas facilities confirmed high usability, strong perceived training value, and positive acceptance across both use cases. This paper describes the system architecture, technical components, AI integration, evaluation results, and deployment considerations.

SECTION 1. INTRODUCTION

Industrial assembly and maintenance of complex electronic equipment — such as edge computing devices deployed in critical infrastructure — demands a skilled workforce capable of performing precise, multi-step procedures under varying conditions. Training these technicians presents a persistent challenge: static documentation and uniform instructional materials do not account for differences in experience level, cognitive state, and on-the-job context.

Extended Reality (XR) technologies offer a promising approach to immersive industrial training, providing three-dimensional visualisation, step-by-step procedural guidance, and simulated environments where technicians can practise without risk to live equipment. However, delivering identical content to every trainee regardless of their real-time condition limits the effectiveness of any training medium, immersive or otherwise.

This whitepaper presents the Pilot 5 application developed within the XR5.0 Horizon Europe project. The system integrates real-time physiological monitoring with constrained generative AI to form a closed adaptive loop: the trainee's biometric state informs when and how training content should be adjusted, and generative AI produces the adapted procedural content in response. The following sections describe the system architecture, technical components, use cases, evaluation results, governance considerations, and deployment lessons.

Use Cases

The pilot addresses the maintenance lifecycle of edge computing devices through two complementary use cases.

UC1 — Personalised Training for Device Assembly. The first use case targets classroom-based training where technicians learn assembly and configuration procedures for edge devices. Trainees wear XR headsets and biometric sensors while following step-by-step procedural content within an immersive environment. The system adapts the training programme in real time based on the trainee's engagement and cognitive load, adjusting instructional granularity, pacing, and content modality to match individual needs.

Figure1: XR training environment for device assembly

UC2 — Remote-Guided Repair. The second use case supports field technicians performing maintenance on deployed equipment in operational environments such as data centers. Technicians use handheld devices (tablets or smartphones) with augmented reality overlays to access procedural guidance, AI-generated troubleshooting content, and contextual documentation. Biometric monitoring detects stress or cognitive overload during complex repair tasks and triggers more detailed diagnostic guidance.

Figure2: Repair instructions

Architecture

Figure 1 presents the system architecture. The Training Management Platform provides centralised management of XR applications, training assets, and authored training programmes. XR training applications are deployed via cloud virtualisation and streamed to client devices. The LLM Engine, grounded in device manuals and technical documentation, communicates with the XR application via API. The Human Digital Twin Platform collects biometric data from the trainee's wearable sensor, processes engagement and cognitive load indicators, and provides personalised training programme adjustments to the XR application.

Figure 3: System architecture for the Pilot 5 biometric-adaptive XR training system.

Two actors interact with the system. The administrator or training manager uses a web-based interface to configure training programmes, manage assets, and monitor trainee progress. The trainee interacts through an XR head-mounted device and a wearable biometric sensor. The architecture supports both immersive headset-based training for classroom environments and handheld device deployments for field operations, connected through a device-agnostic streaming layer.

Components

The following table describes the technical components of the Pilot 5 application.

Technical Component	Description
XR Training Application	Unity-based application built with OpenXR, deployed as a single Android APK supporting both Meta Quest headsets and standard Android devices. Renders procedural training content, 3D models, and AR overlays.
XR Training Asset Repository	Cloud-based repository for managing training materials, programmes, and assets. Supports multi-tenant provisioning with database-per-tenant isolation. RESTful API for asset and programme management.
Training Programs Authoring Tool	Web-based tool for creating and configuring structured training programmes, assigning materials to procedural steps, and managing learning paths.
LLM Engine	Generative AI engine grounded in device-specific technical documentation (manuals, wiring diagrams, fault trees). Produces structured procedural content including training scenarios, troubleshooting guides, and step-by-step instructions.
Human Digital Twin Platform (Clawdite)	Processes biometric data to derive engagement scores, cognitive load estimates, and stress indicators. Generates adaptation recommendations for the active training programme.
Wearable Biometric Sensor	Smartwatch worn during training sessions, capturing heart rate variability, electrodermal activity, and motion-based indicators. Connected via UNP Connector.
Hololight Hub / Stream	Cloud-based streaming and orchestration of XR applications. Manages virtualised XR application instances and streams them to client devices.
Virtualisation Provider	AWS-based infrastructure for running XR application instances in virtual machines, enabling centralised deployment and reducing client-side hardware requirements.

SECTION 3. PILOT EVALUATION

Evaluation Context

The early prototype was evaluated at SPACE Hellas facilities on 5 November 2025 in realistic assembly and maintenance environments. Participants included technicians and assembly workers covering both use cases. The assessment combined structured questionnaires, task-performance observations, and qualitative feedback to measure usability, effectiveness, and user acceptance.

The evaluation infrastructure consisted of Meta Quest 2/3 VR headsets, Google Fit-compatible smartwatch devices for biometric data collection, and an MDUINO 19R PLUS industrial controller for edge device simulation. Software components included the Unity-based XR application streamed via Hologlight, the XR5.0 Training Platform, the Clawdite Human Digital Twin Platform, and the MDUINO Digital Twin for relaying commands between the VR environment and physical devices.

Figure 4: The Evaluation Environment.

The evaluation focused on the XR training application, training platform integration, biometric monitoring via wearable sensors, and real-time device communication. Participants executed assembly and commissioning workflows using the XR-guided step-by-step procedures while wearing biometric sensors, allowing the project team to assess usability, procedural accuracy, interaction responsiveness, and the perceived value of adaptive biometric feedback. The 3D Guardian controller model served as the training target, with participants progressing through structured training programmes retrieved from the cloud-based asset repository. Real-time MQTT-based communication with the physical MDUINO device enabled participants to send configuration commands and monitor device status directly from within the VR environment, bridging the gap between virtual training and operational device interaction.

Results Summary

The following table summarises the evaluation results across key dimensions. Ratings are on a 1–5 scale.

Evaluation Dimension	Avg. Rating	Key Insight
Technical Performance	4.0–4.5	Stable operation, no crashes, responsive interaction, easy hardware setup
Usability and User Experience	4.0–4.5	Intuitive navigation, consistent behaviour, high trust in system responses
Work Impact and Effectiveness	3.8–4.8	Strong improvement in understanding (4.8) and confidence (4.6); efficiency gains emerging (3.8)
Task Load Index	1.6–4.6	Low workload (physical demand 2.8, stress 1.8); high perceived success (4.6)
Social and Economic Impact	3.0–4.8	Strong onboarding value (4.8); sustainability benefits recognised (4.4)
Overall Satisfaction	4.8	Participants recommend continued development toward deployment

Participants reported that immersive step-by-step XR guidance significantly improved their understanding of assembly and repair procedures (4.8) and increased confidence and motivation to perform similar tasks (4.6). The XR environment was rated as closely matching real assembly and repair conditions (4.8), and real-time communication with physical devices was considered effective (4.6). The biometric feedback was perceived as useful for self-awareness during training (4.2), though participants noted that clearer explanation of physiological indicators would strengthen the adaptive features. Workplace safety improvement was rated highly (4.6), and all participants indicated they would recommend the solution for onboarding new employees (4.8). Qualitative feedback highlighted the value of practising in a risk-free environment, clear visualisations, and structured procedural guidance. Suggested improvements included richer interaction options, additional gestures, and tighter integration with existing company systems.

KPI Readiness

The following table summarises the readiness status of pilot performance indicators.

KPI	Status	Notes
Reduction in Assembly Time \geq 20%	Partially Assessed	Indicative measurements suggest target met; participants completed tasks within or below expected thresholds with reduced hesitation
Engagement of Lower-Skilled Technicians \geq 50%	Partially Assessed	Clear increase observed; participants followed workflows independently with reduced supervision
Reduction of Assembly/Repair Costs > 20%	Indicative	Cost impact inferred from time savings and reduced errors; requires automated tracking for validation

Task Execution Efficiency	Assessed	XR guidance improved procedural flow and reduced interruptions
Error and Rework Reduction	Assessed	Fewer errors and less rework observed during XR-supported execution

Deployment Considerations

Environment-Specific Device Strategies. Immersive XR headsets provide an effective training experience in controlled classroom environments. However, field repair operations present different constraints: technicians work in physically confined spaces, need their hands free, and cannot afford the situational awareness reduction of a fully immersive headset. For field scenarios, handheld devices with augmented reality overlays provide a more practical modality. The system accommodates both modes through a device-agnostic design, using a single application build that can be streamed to headsets or run directly on handheld devices.

Interaction Modality. The system supports voice commands as an input modality, but speech-to-text accuracy for technical terminology varies significantly across languages. For less widely supported languages with domain-specific vocabulary, error rates can disrupt the training experience. The system therefore employs a hybrid voice and touch interface, where voice commands handle navigation and confirmations while touch interactions provide reliable fallback for precise selections and text input.

Scalability. The cloud-based architecture enables centralised management and streaming of XR applications across multiple sites. The system also supports local installation of the training asset repository for environments where data sovereignty or network constraints preclude cloud reliance.

Conclusions

The Pilot 5 application demonstrates how biometric monitoring, constrained generative AI, and XR technologies can be integrated into a coherent adaptive training system for industrial maintenance. The closed feedback loop — where physiological data drives content adaptation and generative AI produces the adapted procedural content — provides a practical mechanism for real-time training personalisation that goes beyond static skill-level classification.

Processing physiological data in a workplace training context requires careful attention to regulatory and ethical requirements. Under GDPR, biometric data constitutes special category personal data; the EU AI Act adds further obligations. The pilot's approach is grounded in voluntary participation with genuine informed consent, data minimisation (processing aggregate indicators rather than storing raw signals), and transparency about data collection and usage. A Data Protection Impact Assessment has been conducted to document risks and mitigating measures.

The underlying architecture is not specific to edge device assembly. Physiological monitoring driving content adaptation through a closed loop, with generative AI producing structured procedural output, is applicable to any domain characterised by skilled manual work, variable expertise levels, and safety requirements. Further development will focus on automated performance tracking, deeper system integration, refined adaptive mechanisms, and optimised onboarding and ergonomics to support deployment at scale.

REFERENCES

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